

“NEED & IMPORTANT OF BLENDED LEARNING IN THE ERA OF DIGITAL EDUCATION” IN THE CONTEXT OF NEP 2020

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Abstract

Education is at best, the core of humanity and the foundation of a booming society. In addition to most common beliefs, education means not only learning how to read and write but also the overall development of personality. This is a prominent fact that the need for education has been competent and adequately recognized in the modern world. While the traditional method of imparting or receiving an education has been ample for a pre-digital era, the sudden explosion in technology has overwhelmed the education system significantly, creating an increased demand for more digital-period-specific means of education. Digital education is the innovative integration of modern technology and digital tools to assist the advancement of teaching and learning. It is also known as Technology Enhanced Learning (TEL), computer mediated learning, digital learning, or e-learning. Digital education is the way forward to seeking education through the means of technology and digital devices. The modern educational system is different from than it was few decades before the discrepancy in student demography, their personal traits, globalization of the world economy and Internet technologies has enforced to change it. As a result, many educationalists are exploring newer models of instruction which can transfer and inculcate necessary knowledge, skills, and attitude to meet out these challenges and could produce successful pass-outs to serve the modern society. As educationalists begin to think changing the methods of teaching. Lecture based traditional teaching-learning process as the preferred teaching method by integrating technology in teaching-learning, blended and flipped learning has emerged as approaches of education design.

Key Words: *Technology, Blended learning, Digital Era*

Introduction

Blended learning is the learning environment that involves the integration of technology in the learning process together with traditional instructive practices. Blended learning is a combination of offline i.e. face-to-face, traditional classroom learning and technology based online learning in a way that the one compliments the other. It provides learners with the opportunity to take advantages of both the modes. For example, students might attend classes in a common classroom setting and then supplement the learning by completing coursework through online mode. Again, they can attend the class to clarify any doubts and further discussions if required. Blended learning is often also referred to as “hybrid learning, and can take on a variety of forms in education environments. Teachers may use blended learning techniques on some selected occasions, or can utilize it as a primary teaching method within their set of course. There are two key principles commonly associated with blended learning ii) Students who share information and work with other students directly in a collaborative environment have a more enriched learning experience. ii) Collaboration between students can be improved upon if group activities rely on information gathered from online resources or lessons. Tools and platforms that can be commonly used to

complement classroom teaching in blended learning include Learning Management Systems, Virtual labs, Virtual reality, Videos and interactive video tutorials, various OERs like NPTEL, e-Gyan Kosh and by using desktop/laptop computers, and mobile devices such as tablets and smart phones.

Merits and Characteristics of Blended Learning

Blended learning enables students to explore information or guidance online, which can be accessed student any time they need and classroom learning environment helps to build better connection between the students and the teacher.

- Education is not just about instructional but also learning team-working, interpersonal, self-motivation, discipline and blending learning helps both students and teachers to learn according to their own pace and scheme.
- Extra-co-curricular and other hands-on practices help students to build their social-personal effectively and online learning offers a broad selection of content and information they need for the overall development of their personality.

- Blended learning makes it uncomplicated for learners to communicate about their assignments, report, test, results or else they might need to know from their teachers and makes assessment and evaluation more personalized and effective.
- Blending learning helps students to better opportunity for experiential learning, explore technology and use different tools or techniques for learning, for example, PowerPoint, Virtual classrooms, Video lectures, etc.
- Blended learning improves the quality of education, learning skill greater access to information, assimilation while making teaching learning more systematic and fruitful.
- In the previous year, the time of pandemic have reinforced the fact that life is uncertain and we need to prepare unpleasant situation to ourselves and get ready to keep on this inconstant nature of existence. Similarly, the education system needs to follow methods like blended learning to ensure that the process of learning never stops, different approaches and strategies need to be included or practiced in institutions to be ahead of time.

Importance of Blended Learning

National Education Policy- 2020 Overview

The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) is a well-planned comprehensive policy framework for the future trajectory of education in India. Since the National Policy on Education (NPE) of 1986, it is India's first comprehensive education policy. An extensive change of India's educational system is envisioned by NEP 2020, with a focus on online and blended learning in particular. The policy suggests that, in order to efficiently deliver high-quality education, all educational institutions—from primary to higher education—use online and blended learning approaches. In addition, it proposes for the establishment of a National Education

Technology Mission to guarantee that all educational institutions have access to the technology and infrastructure required for online and blended learning.

According to NEP (2020) of the Indian government, blended learning must be experiential and activity-based. It is not a mere combination of both physical and virtual modes; rather, it is a carefully planned integration of relevant activities in both the modes. "Unless combined with experiential and activity-based learning, online education will tend to become a screen-based education with little emphasis on the social, emotional, and psychomotor components of learning" (National Education Policy, 2020, p. 59).

Importance of Blended Learning

Blended learning is important because its mixture of e-learning and traditional learning and teaching. one method of teaching not fit for all students. But now in present time technologies and resources can prepare the learning experience for each student. Blended learning provides experiences, repeatable, reliable, and reproducible. BL is one that offers flexible time frames that offering them the ability to learn at their own pace and speed and keep students continuously engaged and motivated. Blended learning yields more frequent and more personal, this type of learning allows flexibility for students and teachers.

Students can enjoy individualized learning that suits their study plan through blended tools. It allows students to personalize their learning experiences by using supplementary tools beyond the classroom. Learners can choose the areas that is more important and individualized their learning schedule to accommodate this. blended learning methods is also useful for teachers to sharpen their teaching. This is a modernistic way of teaching that can have a positive impact on a student's learning experience. Increased flexibility, technology-enabled learning, learning, anytime and anywhere and students learn without the barriers of time and location. It can make learning fun the overall result should be to allow the learner to have access to information from anywhere encouraging them to take learning is to their own hands and enjoy the process by doing something interesting and prepares students to learn according to their capacity and capability and also work at digital based job that requires in present scenarios.

Features of Blended Learning

Technology is increasingly becoming an integral part of our lives. Technological invention is also expanding the range of possible solutions that can be brought to bear on teaching and learning. Blended learning makes learning more enjoyable and better involvement of students. A lot merits other methods of teaching. Blended learning focuses on students centric what they learn and how much time they need to learn it well. BL offers a platform to facilitate greater interactivity between student as well as between students and teachers. Complicated topics can be covered in the classroom and since a rest of the content is available online, students can work on learning the subject within a given timeline with a well-planned, blended learning strategy Also digital content like videos, recordings and e-books can be reused, which is an added advantage. Creating a blended learning strategy reduces classroom teaching time and, by digitizing the expertise of talented instructors or subject-matter experts, you can teach more students with world-class content. Blended learning enables collaborative learning environments assignment, discussion, and through its students naturally motivated. Therefore, both online and offline teamwork opportunities Blended learning supports personalized learning: Each person learns in a unique way and blended learning supports it. For example, you can assign reading comprehension passages according to the comprehension level of each student which can prevent unnecessary burdening for students who need to work harder. it provide more scope for communication for both teacher and students and they become more technical and they gained enhance digital fluency.

Role of Teacher in Blended Learning

Teacher has to play an active part differently than the traditional classroom setups. The shift to blended learning has enthused educators to redefine traditional roles of a teacher. The word "facilitator" has emerged as an alternative to "teacher," bringing with it a somewhat diverse focus on teaching learning activities. The facilitator has to put an emphasis on empowering students with the knowledge and skills required to make the use of online material and personalized learning time in most effective manner, guiding students toward the most meaningful learning experience possible. The teacher as facilitators has to focus on following areas:

- ✓ Making available both online and offline course content by developing it and/or by organizing the sources and links of online content useful for the course.
- ✓ Facilitation of communication with students and among students to create a conducive environment to carry on activities.
- ✓ The teachers Guides the learner experience of independent students, and customizing the material wherever possible, in order to reinforce the learning experience.
- ✓ Designing ways of assessing the learners as per the perceived outcomes of learning. With the easy availability and accessibility of technological tools, implementing blended learning is a viable option for institutes looking to integrate technology-enabled learning into their Teaching-learning strategy. You will appreciate that the blended learning has potential to get the best of both TDL and LDL approaches in a given situation. It is up to teachers to utilize it in appropriate way to harness its benefits to increase the effectiveness of teaching learning process.

Role of Students in the BL Environment

Student Must Own Their Learning:

Generous hour opportunities is a concept where students are allowed a certain amount of time. usually, one class period or one hour per week to research or work anything of interest to them. so, this something outside of the classroom learning and something that is students can generate their own ideas about this give students some freedom to work on things that the really enjoy but also be learning at the same time and have assistance from the teacher.

Students Must Become A Collaborator

In a blended learning environment, students must become active collaborators to enhance their learning experience. Collaboration involves working with peers, sharing ideas, and solving problems together through both in-face to face and online platforms. Students are engaging in group discussions, projects, and peer feedback, and develop communication, teamwork, and critical thinking skills in the blended learning classroom. This collaborative approach fosters a deeper understanding of content and encourages the exchange of diverse perspectives. Online tools such as forums, video calls, and shared documents make collaboration more accessible and effective. As collaborators, students take ownership of their learning and contribute meaningfully to a dynamic and interactive educational environment. So that we can use our best communication in a classroom.

Students Must Become A Communicator:

In a blended learning (BL) environment, students must become effective communicators to succeed. Communication is essential for expressing ideas clearly, asking questions, and engaging in meaningful dialogue with peers and instructors, both online and in face-to-face settings. Students must actively participate in discussions, provide constructive feedback, and collaborate using digital tools such as emails, forums, and video conferencing. Being a good communicator helps build understanding, resolve misunderstandings, and create a

supportive learning environment. It also develops confidence and interpersonal skills. In BL, communication bridges the gap between physical and virtual classrooms, ensuring continuous and active learning throughout the course.

Students Must Become A Creator:

In a blended learning environment, most importantly, the learner not only gains knowledge but also engages in various activities such as making videos, creating projects, giving presentations, and completing other study-related tasks. This shows that they have their own learning space to create something new and that they are continuously learning.

This process helps them think critically, generate new ideas, and solve problems. By using digital tools and platforms, students can express their learning in diverse and personalized ways. Creating also encourages deeper engagement with the subject matter, as students take ownership of their work. In blended learning, being a creator transforms students into active participants in a dynamic and learner-centered environment.

Students Must Become A Researcher:

Learners must develop as researchers in a blended learning (BL) setting by proactively analyzing and successfully utilizing data from a variety of sources. Creating enquiries, researching subjects, and critically assessing print and digital materials are all part of this job. Students gain inquiry-based skills as researchers, which foster better understanding and self-directed learning. Students can access a variety of online databases, journals, and multimedia resources through blended learning, which helps them carry out fruitful study.

Vaughan, Cleveland-Innes, and Garrison (2013) assert that BL cultivates critical thinking and inquiry, two qualities that are crucial for a researcher. Learners who embrace this position develop into independent learners who are ready for both intellectual and practical difficulties.

Prepares Students for the Future

BL offers an aggregation of real-world skills, that directly translate into life skills, from:

- ✓ Research skill
- ✓ Self-learning
- ✓ Self-engagement
- ✓ Helps to develop a 'self-driving force'
- ✓ Better decision making
- ✓ Offers a larger sense of liability
- ✓ Digital literacy

Needs of Blended Learning in the Era of Digital Education

In a traditional classroom teaching one teacher involved for ten or more students, teachers are limited in how much time they can spend in classroom and this model has been limited by total numbers up to this point. The pace of instruction must continue at an average speed. Teachers have been teaching to the middle, which can be too fast for some learners and too slow for others and teacher is knowledge provider in a traditional classroom, it can be difficult for teachers to determine exactly how well each student knows a particular concept because they are responsible for so many students and so many concepts. Now, technology is available to support teachers and allow

them to individualize instruction. Programs can gather data, engage students, and maintain instruction while the teacher facilitates and provides one-to-one support for unique learning styles. Teachers are vital to the success of our students, and as technology evolves, it should be used to help them their learners.

The time is changing so fast, need of technology and demand for technological skills makes it clear that it's time for teachers to assessment of their role in the classroom and determine if their curriculum is designed to help students become successful in present and upcoming time. As the delivery of content shifts from the teacher to a wide variety of online and traditional media sources, many teachers feel like their role is changing. But, on the contrary to the role of the teacher is crucial to student success than ever before.

The role of teachers in the 21st century is to guide students in dealing with massive amounts of content, to develop the skills and understanding necessary to use technology as an effective way and helps in collaboration of students and teachers on different projects. Different learners have different style blended learning allows for students/trainees to take information home and have own time to understand it without the pressure of keeping up with the rest of the class. quizzing and testing online that allows trainers to have more time to educate in the physical classroom environmental it is also a good way to have a quick overview of learner's progress.

All the educational institution will have to create a blended learning Environment; the payoff is a highly engaging

classroom that promotes students need and interest. Flexible Pedagogy and Learning the rich resources of advance e-learning tools such as digital textbooks, digital library, multimedia's colorful illustrations, and web-based lessons, are most suitable for e- learning or any content, subject, class (Alasraj Alharbi, 2014). Most of learners prefer the blended learning environment because it allows them to choose their own time and place. learners enjoy the adaptability and freedom of learning being able to choose this kind of environment and they prefer such as face to face, online, or hybrid. Most of the instructor and trainer picks the BL for three reasons: (1) improved pedagogy, (2) increased access and flexibility, and (3) increased cost-effectiveness Teacher-Developed Blended Learning Model the traditional classroom, learning is limited to what the teacher teaches within the face-to-face environment, use of the online digital curriculum facilitates learners' distinctive proficiency skills with their own elastic schedule.

Conclusion

Bl mode is to be used world-wide to help learners develop 21st century digital skills along with the effective learning and skill development related to the subject-domains. Bl should be carefully implemented in all the educational institution. We need more research on the design of blended environments and how trainer and learners engage in the act of teaching and learning in these environments. Educational institutions and teachers in making the effective use of the technology and should be necessarily implemented in the primary to higher education institution of our country.

References

- Vaughan, N., Cleveland-Innes, M., & Garrison, D. R. (2013). *Teaching in blended learning environments: Creating and sustaining communities of inquiry*. Athabasca University Press.
- Banditvilai, C. (2016). Enhancing students' language skills through blended learning. *Electronic Journal of eLearning*, 14(3), 10.
- Dilekli, Y. (2017). The relationships between critical thinking skills and learning styles of gifted students. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 3(4), 69-96.
- Changwong, K., Sukkamart, A. & Sisan, B. (2018). Critical thinking skill development: analysis of a new learning management model for Thai high schools. *Journal of International Studies*, 11(2).
- Dwiyogo, W. D. (2018a). Developing a blended learning-based method for problem-solving in capability learning. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 17(1), 11.
- Cahyani, N. I., & Azizah, U. (2019). Penerapan Model Pembelajaran Inkuiri Terbimbing Untuk Melatihkan Keterampilan Berpikir Kritis Siswa Pada Materi Laju Reaksi Kelas XI SMA. *Unesa Journal of Chemical Education*, 8(3).
- Blau, I., Shamir-Inbal, T., & Avdiel, O. (2020). How does the pedagogical design of a technology-enhanced collaborative academic course promote digital literacies, self-regulation, and perceived learning of students? *The internet and higher education*, 45, 100722.
- <https://www.jirs.ac.in/blogs/introduction-to-digital-education-and-its-benefits-for-students>
- https://www.ugc.ac.in/pdfnews/6100340_Concept-Note-Blended-Mode-of-Teaching-and-Learning.pdf
- https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358425341_Blen ded_Learning_Innovative_challenge_faced_by_students_at_Uni versity_level_in_Pakistan
- https://scholar.google.co.in/scholar?q=Blended+learning+eff ectiveness:+the+relationship+between+student+characterist ics,+design+features+and+outcomes&hl=en&as_sdt=0&as_vis =1&oi=scholar